

time in the grains indicated that *R. oryzae* is a seedborne pathogen and that infested seeds may serve as a primary source of inoculum.

R. oryzae usually grew over or dominated other associated organisms on

PDA. Sometimes it grew in mixed culture with other fast-growing fungi, or formed distinct individual colonies side by side with colonies of other organisms. Other fungal species that were commonly encountered during the study, in the

order of their frequency of isolation, were *Fusarium*, *Curvularia*, *Nigrospora*, *Helminthosporium*, *Phoma*, *Cercospora*, and other unidentified and non-sporulating fungi. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in China

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In March 1979, the senior author found in 3 lines of hybrid rice about 60 hills infected by a disease in an experimental plot in Zhonghwa country, Guangdong, PROC. The diseased plants were stunted and their leaves were green but ragged and twisted.

The diseased hills were transplanted in pots and kept at GAAS. At later growth stages, their flag leaves were short, distorted, and occasionally ragged. Numerous nodal panicles were produced but many were incompletely exerted and most of the grains were empty (see figure). A few swollen veins were found on the lower surface of leaf blades and the outer surface of leaf sheaths. All the symptoms were similar to those of rice ragged stunt disease in the Philippines.

Brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens* were confined on diseased plants for acquisition feeding. The viruliferous

A rice hill infected with ragged stunt disease in China.

insects were then used to inoculate healthy seedlings, which then developed the above-mentioned symptoms, indicating that brown planthoppers could transmit the disease.

The results identify the symptoms of the disease found in Zhonghwa as those of rice ragged stunt in the Philippines. This may be the first record of ragged stunt in China. ■

Effectiveness of fungicides in the control of blast (neck rot)

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No suitable chemicals to control blast (neck rot) infection caused by *Piricularia oryzae* has been reported in Uttar Pradesh. Therefore the relative effectiveness of some fungicides was tested in the field.

Foliar sprays of four fungicides — edifenphos, Miltox, blue copper, and

Relative effectiveness of some fungicides on blast (neck rot) incidence and grain yield of paddy during kharif seasons of 1974–75 and 1975–76.

Fungicide	Dose (% active ingredient)	Blast (neck rot) incidence (%) (mean of 4 replicates)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1974–75	1975–76	1974–75	1975–76
Edifenphos	0.1	2.1	2.8	3.3	3.4
Miltox	0.25	4.3	5.4	3.0	2.9
Blue copper	0.30	7.0	6.0	2.7	2.2
Kitazin 17%	988 kg/ha	10.0	8.6	2.1	1.9
Control	—	12.6	10.3	1.7	1.4
C.D. @5% (critical deviation)				2.20	4.25

Kitazin—were tested on the susceptible variety Basmati 370 in a randomized

block design. Fertilizer was applied at 80 kg N/ha. Spraying was done 25, 35,